

Teaching Audio Programming using the Neonlicht Engine

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ABSTRACT

In the following text, we describe the ongoing development of an efficient, easy to use, scalable synthesizer engine: Neonlicht. Neonlicht has been developed with the objective to be used as a teaching tool as part of a study program in digital media. With the system we like to improve the quality of teaching in the subject area of audio programming.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the following text, we describe the ongoing development of an efficient, easy to use, scalable synthesizer engine: Neonlicht. Neonlicht has been developed with the objective to be used as a teaching tool as part of a study program in digital media. With the system we like to improve the quality of teaching in the subject area of audio programming.

A rather large didactic problem is found, when looking at the current situation of many students of digital media. On the one hand students tend to have a high affinity towards using the the computer as a media system. Indeed the computer is used to consume the entire spectrum of digital media. At the same time though the access to the computer as a system for software *development* becomes increasingly more difficult. Similar perceptions relating to work and study behaviour are now observable in many study programs, which is at least the author's estimation after a number of discussions with teaching colleagues in a number of countries.

2. SCHEDULE OF A CURRENT AUDIO PROGRAMMING COURSE

Our starting point for the instructional design of the current course was the insight that students have to be carefully guided in order to get access to the complex topics of audio programming. A larger fraction of them displays deficits in both programming skills, as well as in mathematical foundations. Furthermore using mathematics is often referred to as being "uncreative" and leads to immediate "learning rigor mortis".

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As a basic precondition our course had to be constructed in a *practice oriented* way: the acquisition of knowledge through practical application often leads to better results in understanding the instructional material.

The introductory phase of the course was started by building (or to be more accurate: by assembling) physical synthesizers: for this two Moog¹ systems were purchased. This entry phase was very successful. Students loved experimenting with the synthesizers. For the subsequent analysis of the Moog's functionality and its simulation on the computer Pure Data was used (see [1]). Again, the entry threshold to this technology is relatively low, since software development is supported by a fairly intuitive graphic user interface.

Figure 1. Neonlicht runs on a Raspberry PI 3 (the image displays it's predecessor, the Raspberry 2).

Moreover, the author bought two CCRMA Satellite Systems² at an ICMC/SMC 2014 workshop in Athens. In these systems, Pure Data runs on a Raspberry 1. Via an additional Arduino it becomes possible to connect external hardware components to the system and then use them as hardware controls for Pure Data. The students were therefore able to run larger parts of their Pure Data patches on this hardware setup.

The course then continued with a step by step introduction to the most common synthesis methods. The theory parts were supported by corresponding practical exercises.

In the final phase of the course each student had to define, plan and implement a freely chosen individual project. The outcomes were very pleasing: amongst other things the students developed a guitar effect processor with PureData running on a Raspberry Pi 2, a gesture-based musical instrument utilizing Wii controllers and an 8bit sound machine.

¹ <http://www.moogmusic.com/products/Werkstatt>

² <https://ccrma.stanford.edu/eberdahl/Satellite/>

Overall, the results were positive, but at the same time demonstrated the problems very clearly. The students were very disappointed of the lack in practicality of the systems used. They felt that the development work was in many ways a to high challenge, as the system did not support error tracking and debugging well, modularization is not well supported when developing larger systems, the performance of the systems is very limited and only a rather poor system integration could be achieved.

In total, they had the impression that you can only build simple test and experimental systems, but when it comes to building "real", larger systems, these tools are not suitable.

3. NEONLICHT: REQUIREMENTS

The starting point for the development of Neonlicht, an engine for the efficient programming of synthesizers and audio processing components, thus was the insight, that although there is a variety of systems for audio programming, that none of the proposed approaches met the educational requirements of the current course. In sum, with Neonlicht we therefore try to implement the following requirements:

- simplicity of the underlying program structure
- comparability with existing standard audio applications (Pure Data, STK ([2]), ChucK ([3]), SuperCollider ([4]) etc.), allowing for an easy transition
- a reduction (!) in the number of audio functions on the didactically relevant
- flexibility and easy expandability of the basic functions
- ease of installation of the system
- avoiding if possible all programming constructs that go beyond basic knowledge of object oriented programming (in Java) (especially use of pointers and memory management)
- low resource consumption, enabling the system to run on simple and cheap hardware
- high (professional) quality of synthesis and audio output
- a clear logical and physical separation of engine and control
- maximum portability, at least for Linux/Unix based systems

3.1 Using the Raspberry Pi 3

It is a key technical requirement in the development of the Neonlicht engine to make it run on a current Raspberry Pi 3 (see [5]). In its third generation this micro-computer is so powerful, that the students will be able to programm and experiment directly on the machine. In combination

with a low-cost USB audio card and a standard MIDI controller musical instruments can be developed that can even be used in live situations.

Despite of the relatively high performance of the Raspberry 3, it is still necessary to implement Neonlicht as efficiently as possible and also to enable the application developer to make efficient use of the machine. Based on these considerations, we chose to use C++ directly, with no higher language abstraction built on top of it. However, we try to define a high level of abstraction for Neonlicht, and focus on the object-oriented features of C++. By this we hope to reduce the amount of code writing and simultaneously focus on the audio processing code.

Two effects can be achieved by the (initial) restriction onto the Raspberry Pi. First, the systems can be inexpensively purchased in larger numbers and then passed on to students (either for a limited time or permanently). These *identical* sets are then available in the classroom, which greatly facilitates the explanations of the lecturer. Secondly, it is possible to use the small computer in virtually any location without major problems. Thus, it will become much simpler to present the projects of the students in various public contexts.

Figure 2. The system architecture of the Neonlicht engine.

4. NEONLICHT: BUILDING THE SYNTHESIZER ENGINE

When planning Neonlicht we assumed that the communication between the operating system and the audio hardware could be realized with existing software libraries.

For audio input and output we chose *RTAudio* and correspondingly *RTMidi* for communication with and control of the Midi hardware (see [2]). These libraries are very mature and compile and run fine on the Raspberry. They are thus a very stable foundation for the abstraction that should be made by Neonlicht.

Besides using *RTAudio/RTMidi*, Neonlicht also uses a few parts of the *STK*. This takeover of functionality includes four standard filter classes that are implemented in the *STK*. As these filters are not a central part of the intended functionality of the system, we simply used what has already been implemented in a very reliable way. In

addition, this takeover demonstrates how to integrate functions from other libraries into the Neonlight architecture.

For the implementation of the network communication, the OSC library *oscpack* (see [6]) was used. The loading and storing of configuration data is done with *config4star* (see [7]). Unfortunately, these two libraries are apparently no longer being developed. For this reason the complete source code of the libraries has been integrated into the distribution of Neonlight as a 3rd party software. This ensures, that at least the current state of the libraries will be available on a near term basis. The licenses of the two libraries allow for such redistribution.

4.1 Audio programming with Neonlight

The system architecture of Neonlight separates

- the code for the audio processing and
- the code for the control via GUI or MIDI

from the actual engine (see Figure 2).

The application developer has to implement a plugin, a so called *Sound Unit*. For doing this a simple interface with four methods has been defined. When configuring a Neonlight application the sound unit must be passed on to the engine. Neonlight controls the sound unit and forwards the generated samples on to the audio hardware.

The implementation of the sound units follows the well established approach of unit generators (see [8]). Neonlight itself currently provides about 60 unit generators. From these, more complex sound units are constructed, which are then also unit generators and can be used to recursively build up more complex units. For students who have mastered the concept of unit generators, the development of an audio system in Neonlight turns out to be very comprehensible.

By this approach the amount of application code is reduced greatly. In order to implement a simple subtractive synthesizer called *Workshop-16*, that simulates the functionality of the provided Moog systems, only 34 lines of audio code had to be written. The granularity of the used unit generators corresponds to that of comparable current systems. The code for the system control is a little longer, but basically consists of a mapping of command strings to system parameters.

In the end the user has access to a synthesizer, that is fully playable with a standard Midi Controller, being able to change sound parameters in real time. The software runs on a Raspberry 3, causing rarely more the 10% system load. This number is taken on the development system, where a full X-Server is running, taking away considerable amounts of processing time.

Reliable statements about the exact performance of the engine can not yet be made, although there are measurements on the runtime behavior of some of the unit generators. The audio sampling rate of 44.1 KHz corresponds to a maximum tick()-time of 22.675 microseconds. This interval must not be exceeded by the audio processing, since otherwise drop outs in the audio stream will occur. As can be taken from the data in table 1 the average processing

times of the unit generators listed are significantly below this threshold.

<i>unit generator</i>	<i>time in μs</i>
noise1→tick();	0.121
saw1→tick();	0.0314
mixer1→tick();	0.447
square1→tick();	0.0281
onelf→tick();	0.0389
eg1→tick();	0.053
cosine1→tick();	0.100
phasor1→tick();	0.052
Workshop-16→tick();	1.472

Table 1. Time measurements on a Raspberry 3 of a single tick() function call in a subset of the implemented unit generators. The maximum time span must be less than 22.675 μ s, otherwise audio drop outs will occur.

According to these measurements, the system has sufficient performance reserves to implement more complex real-time audio systems. In theory up to 14 Workshop-16 systems can run in parallel on the Raspberry 3!

The most complex code part when developing a synthesizer with Neonlight turns out to be the implementation of the graphical user interface. Of course the user can always do without implementing a GUI, as it is not in any way required by the Neonlight architecture.

Figure 3. The ncurses interface of the Workshop-16 synthesizer. The GUI of a sound unit developed for Neonlight could be implemented in almost any technology. For this presentation we have chosen to show a very basic, (and very retro) text based version running in a standard terminal window.

4.2 Integration of a GUI

Figure 3 shows the exemplary implementation a graphical user interface for a more complex sound unit. In this case, it is the simulation of a synthesizer with simple subtractive synthesis. The synthesizer uses standard components

(VCO, VCF, ADSR, LFO etc.) in a standard routing configuration. Accordingly, the user interface has been designed: the central parameters of each component can be controlled and the signal routing can be adjusted within certain limits.

As you can see the presented GUI is realized using a very reduced, text oriented design. By this, we wanted to point out that the user interface can be realized in any technology, including text based UIs, web based UIs or application based UIs. The developer is free to choose from any technology, as long as it provides the ability to communicate with Neonlicht via OSC.

5. USING NEONLICHT: FIRST IMPRESSIONS

The next iteration of the audio programming course will be held in the up coming winter semester. In order to get a first impression of whether Neonlicht can be considered a didactically meaningful tool, we introduced Neonlicht to the participants of last year's course. In a 1-day seminar they were asked to try to port their audio applications to Neonlicht. This is admittedly a slightly different situation than a standard course, as the students have significantly higher knowledge in audio programming. In fact, the students responded very positively to the engine. No one has had any experience in programming in C++, still, with the support of the teachers, they managed to successfully reimplement large parts of their audio applications. They were particularly inspired by the fact that, at the end of the day, a single executable program existed, that performed the complete audio processing.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have provided an overview of the synthesizer engine Neonlicht. The system is oriented towards the efficient development of audio applications on the Raspberry 3 and offers a high level of abstraction.

In order to have a sufficient performance, Neonlicht omitted the development of a virtual machine with an associated interpreter for a domain-specific language. Instead, the abstraction provided by Neonlicht should facilitate the immediate implementation of audio processing units in C++.

Overall, the illustrated approach of Neonlicht integrates well with a didactic concept of a stepwise teaching method with practical exercises, where existing tools are used to teach basic concepts of audio programming.

By the subsequent implementation of these processes in Neonlicht students are able to transfer the learned concepts into powerful audio applications.

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